

SOME CONSIDERATIONS ABOUT THE LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF SOME ANTI-MEANING UNITS USED IN TAHIR MALIK'S WORK "HUMAN PROPERTY"

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Abstract. In this article, Tahir Malik's work "Human Property" is proved by several examples of the expression of phraseological units with contradictory meanings. By using a series of contrasting units, the writer will have the opportunity to emphasize different concepts, signs, situations, and images.

Key words and phrases: phraseological units, phraseostylistic devices, contextual contrast, intercategory antonymy, individual character.

Phraseological expressions, which are unique figurative expressions of conclusions drawn by the people based on getting to the bottom of various events in life, evaluating various situations of action, summarizing large and small experiences, are almost always poetically relevant in the artistic text. That is why phrases have a special place in the linguopoetic analysis of the artistic text. Since figurativeness is always noticeable from phrases, since composition is the priority in the semantic structure, they serve the artistic content more actively than words. Tahir Malik used expressions very effectively in his work. Each phrase is chosen correctly, so that the language of the work is attractive and impressive.

The language of the work is also important for the idea advanced by the writer to reach the masses of readers. In fact, the language of the work is characterized by the conciseness and smoothness of expressions, the use of words in their proper place in the interpretation of that idea. Every writer goes through the "trouble of choosing words and phrases" in order to ensure that the language of the work is juicy, artistic and impressive, trying to find units that will please the reader, over and over again on phrases that are not spilled. gets confused and in the process of work acquires artistic tools that allow to create a full-fledged image. The extent to which such tools are used depends on the skill and ability of the artist. Such opportunities are innumerable in the national language, and they require a writer and a speaker who works with word material to spend all their energy and do a lot of creative work. The uniqueness of the writer's style, the individual features of his language are revealed due to the rich possibilities of

choosing the means of expression available in the common language. In addition to providing the writer with all the tools in his vocabulary, the universal language gives the writer the opportunity to choose from them. In addition to providing templates of constructions, it also provides an opportunity to choose from various variants of word, phrase and sentence constructions.

Words with opposite meanings are antonyms. Antonyms are of great importance in written and spoken speech. They make the idea expressive and effective. That is why they are widely used in art.

Tahir Malik created unique examples of the art of contrast, contrast, opposition, created on the basis of units with opposite meanings in the work "Human Property". By using a series of contrasting units, the writer will have the opportunity to emphasize different concepts, signs, situations, and images. As in all living languages, the role of oral and written literature in the development of the Uzbek language is incomparable. The work "Mankind's Property" written by the talented writer Tahir Malik, dedicated to the issues of spirituality, education and faith, can be called the "Book of Morals". Tahir Malik created this work by our people. used phraseological units that express a unique image with great skill in fiction. A correctly chosen phraseological unit gives the essence of the work a special spirit. This makes the work more effective and perfect. rode

We observe that the phraseological contradiction used in the work refers to noun, adjective and verb categories. For example, antonymic phraseology of the verb group: to have a bird of happiness land on one's head – to be in a tizzy:

Our Prophet (pbuh) said, "The house of a Muslim is like a garden of paradise". The example of this is that a bird of happiness landed on the head of a husband who married a girl who "grew up in paradise". But in order for the bird of happiness to land, it must have grown up in paradise. (p. 103) – If he marries a girl of a higher status than himself, the wife may be proud of her father's luxury and luxury and despise her husband. In it, the head of any husband will be in trouble. (page 103)

to get angry – to reach the sky:

–Is this person dead or still alive? Shan asked his companion.

His companion became even more angry:

– Now I want to see a fool like you, whose life has been ruined. It is not a wise person to ask whether a corpse being carried to the cemetery is alive or dead. Please don't talk anymore. If you talk, I'm losing my heart. (page 102) – I came to take you home. If you please go, see my children and make my sick wife happy

with your visit, my head would reach the sky in front of my relatives and friends.
(page 133)

who missed the opportunity - gained the opportunity: Then the Messenger of Allah (pbuh) said: "When I was going to the pulpit, Gabriel came and told me that his mother and father could not go to Paradise during their lifetime or while one of them was still alive, taking their consent and Let the child who missed this opportunity rub his nose on the ground!" - they said. I also said ``Amen". (p. 61) – At this point, we need to study and solve the conflict between two people as a social issue, not just a family conflict. We should consider these as minor defects that can be corrected rather than unnecessary pain. (page 98)

antonymic phraseology of nouns:

the lightness of his face–the darkness of his face: If a father's actions are absorbed by his child, his behavior will be sly. Investigative supervision of the child ensures the light of the parent's face. (p. 9) – We have come across many examples in life about the instability of love between a man and a woman. Today, "I love you dearly, the world is dark for me without you!" "If you look at him tomorrow, you will see the blackness of his face" and look at each other. (page 32)

antonymic phraseology related to the quality category:

a pure heart - an impure heart: Love is so stubborn that in front of him the king and the slave are equal, he is so oppressive that in his eyes both the dirty and the wicked and the lover with a pure heart are the same... (p. 22); Let the wife be pure nihad (pure nature) and pure heart; Kadbonu (working housewife) be a friend to her husband. Let him be imaginative, pious, short-tongued, and a good custodian of property. They say that a good wife is the joy of her husband and her life. (page 99) – But... If only there were no such "but" in life... In life, there are mothers with impure hearts who lose their children, and there are those who are deprived of the right to motherhood. (page 55)

Phraseological ambiguity is a necessary tool for artistic text, first of all, according to the connotative meaning inherent in the phrase, and secondly, according to the expressiveness based on the opposition of phrases: If the will is truly intelligent if it is powered, it will overcome. (p. 12) – After a while, when they came to the same place again, they did not see that strange young man in the garden, and asked him where he was. People:

–He went crazy and climbed the mountain, - they answer. (page 34) In the author's work, the lexical-phraseological conflict of meaning also ensured the clarity and expressiveness of the image: I preferred to use the style of calling to

my heart. Because I think that every person should educate himself first. Each of us must be able to control ourselves, especially our mind. (page 2)

Here, "self-discipline" and "being able to control our mind" are lexical-phraseological antonyms.

Tahir Malik created unique examples of contextual conflicting meaning; managed to exaggerate the contradictions and contrasts between events, actions, and mental-spiritual processes. In Uzbek, the words "happiness" and "tightness" are not antonyms, but in general there is some quantitative contradiction between them. However, it is noticeable that the contradictory meaning in them acquires such a characteristic in the context, that is, in the artistic speech: "Now I am happy about the wife, but I am depressed about the livelihood." In order to exaggerate the strong contrast between the mental states of the characters in the works, a few words from a certain contextual synonymous line are immediately contrasted with several units from another contextual synonymous line: even if it is overflowing, one should not forget morality: a person should cultivate his spiritual aspects, conscience and ego, be able to control his passion, abandon bad habits, and direct his scientific achievements to the benefit of humanity. Otherwise, he may go astray. (p. 13)

Therefore, units such as "educating spiritual aspects", "educating conscience and ego", "being able to control one's passion", "giving up bad habits", "directing one's scientific achievements for the benefit of mankind" are "on the right path" the phrase "to lose weight". opposed.

It is known that the opposite meaning occurs within the same category of words. But even in words belonging to different word groups, there may be a contradiction between certain symbols in the meaning. For example, in the meaning of the word "up" belonging to the adjective group, the meaning "directed to the top" is the main one, and in the word "wither" belonging to the verb group, "the state of lifelessness" is the leading one. It is very difficult to imagine the spiritual conflict between these two words. Some researchers call such a contradictory meaning by the name of "intercategory antonymy". Such conflicting meanings were also used effectively in the works, and this phenomenon also served for the dark expressive image of the writer: "He was looking for a higher level, the times have changed, he faded away."

In this case, the context gives antonymy between different word groups, these can be called contextual antonyms.

Many such words can be found in the work. Each antonymic unit has its own synonymous line, and it is possible to choose a certain one according to the text.

Antonymous units are clearly felt in the text, their specific meaning is very important for the text. Tahir Malik's original language skill is best seen in his use of antonymic units for the purposes of clarity of image and giving way to a certain point in the expression.

Phraseological units contribute to demonstrating the closeness and vitality of the language of Tahir Malik's work "Human Property". The fact that such incomparable tools have an important place in our language as an active speech unit to this day reflects the incomparable and richness of the unique national views and cultural aspects of our people. The unchanged and reworked phraseological units used in Tahir Malik's work "People's Property" can fulfill the role of incomparable phraseological tools in expressing Uzbek national-cultural features. The writer effectively used phraseological expressions as a means of individualizing the characters' speech.

The expressions used in the stories of Tahir Malik are observed both in the speech of the hero and in the speech of the author. Often, the writer effectively uses expressions to create funny situations. As a result, the language of the work was attractive and impressive.

There are many such examples.

In a work of art, the creator selects and uses various tools available in the language in accordance with the purpose. The units that contribute to increasing the aesthetic value of the work show the artist's skill. A skilled creator, along with existing units, invents new expressions himself or gives a new "color" to the content of lexemes in the language based on the speech situation. Some of them contribute to the enrichment of the vocabulary of the language based on the standards of the literary language over time, and some remain specific to a particular speech.

Phraseological tools that create connotative meaning show the artist's skill and style, taking into account that the work is more artistic, in order to determine the linguopoetic value of poetic actualized phraseological tools in Tahir Malik's artistic text, special attention is paid to phraseological polysemy, phraseological homonymy, synonymy, phraseological antonymy, phraseological graduonymy, etc. was directed. Our analysis shows that Tahir Malik used expressions very effectively. In general, the expression of expressions in an artistic work is very wide and diverse. This can be clearly seen in Tahir Malik's work "Human Property". In this work of Tahir Malik, there are many expressions used to show the mental states of people. If the work has no place, the phrase is not used. They play an important role in enhancing image quality.

Tahir Malik's work reminds of a rippling ocean full of jewels and pearls. The more you dive into it, the more you feel its unique beauty and richness. The author's works are enriched with unique artistry, charm, and philosophical expressions, which are not found in other creators, contribute to the enrichment of the treasure of our national language and culture.

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